

Munir's Minimal Intelligence Theory

Multiple intelligence is a nebulous concept, driven by cluttered philosophy, underlying a complex set of higher expectations. The concept is socially and culturally biased and lacks practical application and empirical evidence. Although intelligence is not a single-axis concept, and individuals may possess multiple intelligence, Gardner has portrayed intelligence too broadly. He hypnotized people to look at intelligence categorically- all elite and judgmental- ignoring the crucial concept that applies to all- minimal intelligence.

Dr. Munir Moosa Sadruddin coined the minimal intelligence theory to value human identity. According to him, "Keeping intelligence to a bare minimum simplifies, and neutralizes higher expectations. It is characterized by performing simple tasks or understanding basic concepts with minimum effort to achieve the desired or undesirable outcomes at each educational stage. Stop momentary observations! Rely more on exposure than experience. Intelligence is beyond intelligence, emotional, social, or adversity quotients. No psychometric test can assess human intelligence to perfection. Differentiating human intelligence into specific modalities underestimates the power of minimal intelligence that every human possesses."

According to this theory, academia should assess learners not only based on their age and grades but also by evaluating their progress and comparing their recent performance to their past results. It should not be assumed that a learner's most recent performance will always surpass their previous achievements, as fluctuations are expected, and this is entirely natural. Hence, it is important to employ multiple modes of assessment in a recurring manner to ensure comprehensive evaluations of a learner's progress.